

THE IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE TEACHING IN FORMING THE SCIENTIFIC WORLD VIEW OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *A person's worldview helps him to be in a worthy place in society. That is why it is important to pay attention to it from the first stages of education. As a result of taking a serious look at this issue in primary education, it is possible to help the young generation to take a valuable place in society for themselves and for the state. To achieve this, first of all, it is necessary to achieve the formation of a scientific worldview in primary school students. Recognizing its profound importance, this article focuses on the development of the scientific worldview of primary school students, the importance of the subject of the mother tongue taught in the primary education of general schools, primary school will be devoted to feedback on the factors of formation and formation of scientific worldview in students.*

Keywords: *language, elementary school students, worldview, scientific worldview, thinking, scientific knowledge.*

Today, in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, where great reforms are being implemented, the existence of independent thinking young people is the need of the times, because only people who have a personal worldview will be able to achieve success that ensures the development of society. One of the main factors of the policy carried out in the republic is the development and upbringing of talented individuals with deep thinking, independent outlook.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "If we pay attention to the realization of the abilities of our children from childhood and mobilize all our opportunities for their maturity, many more Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbek will grow up in our country, I believe it." they expressed their confidence in the youth in front of the people. In this regard, today's education system, globalization processes, it is important for the teacher to educate the students of the general education school to be fully mature, intellectually capable, free-thinking, fluent, mature, perfect human beings' responsibility.

In-depth learning of the fundamentals of subjects recommended as subjects of study in educational institutions by students helps to form a broad scientific worldview in them. It is necessary for teachers to take care of the formation of a scientific worldview in students and to constantly pay attention to the practical application of the scientific knowledge acquired by them. As primary education teachers familiarize students with one or other laws and their essence, they teach students to use them in various life situations or to have a consistent, systematic, continuous and purposeful education. the establishment of education, his active participation in the process of social relations of various directions and contents, and also achieves self-education.

Worldview is a set of ideas and views about the world surrounding a person, his definition in this world, and his relationship with reality. The system of philosophical, scientific, political, legal, ethical, aesthetic ideals and beliefs of these people is also counted. Worldview connects the general direction of human activity and behavior. A worldview is a set of views, concepts and ideas about the surrounding world, that is, concepts about nature, society and thinking.

It is known that the scientific outlook of students is formed during the whole school education, because as students move from grade to grade, they learn more and more about the real world, which affects their educational activities and socially useful work activities. goes around. It is an increasingly versatile and dynamic process. It is in primary school students that they get used to independent work of a cognitive nature based on the preparation for extracurricular activities on a certain topic or the performance of initial work related to the analysis of work. scientific outlook develops.

A schoolchild is an active, developing person, which is evident not only in the fact that he tries to do something himself, but also in the fact that he likes to learn how this or that object is made. In this, it is necessary to rely on the student's desire to get acquainted with people's work, because work is a large sphere of the surrounding world, the basis of social life. For this reason, elementary school students are given the elements of a scientific worldview, and the foundations of realistic views of nature and social life phenomena are created in accordance with the perspective of forming a holistic worldview. Excursions to production enterprises are certainly appropriate, considering that they will give elementary school students a lot of knowledge.

It is known that formation of a scientific outlook is carried out in two ways: experience and logic (mind). Therefore, a person should rely on the wise thoughts of past thinkers about life and personal life experience and knowledge that he has accumulated. This is evidenced by the fact that the consciousness of people does not determine their existence, but the existence of material life conditions determines their consciousness. Therefore, the scientific worldview is not a simple phenomenon that happens to everyone, but depends on the level of theoretical and practical knowledge of a person. The entire population of the country that is building a great future state can rise not only by doing business, religion, and trade, but also by developing production, science, knowing world languages, and paying first-class attention to enlightenment in general. understanding is also very important in forming a worldview.

One of the tasks of educating students is to form elements of a scientific worldview in them. In solving this task, the main condition for working according to the purpose is the issue of successful development of the student as a person. And there are some factors that confirm this in practice. These factors serve to determine the method of formation of elements of scientific worldview in students in connection with language teaching. They appear in the following order:

The essence of language as a social phenomenon is to express its communication (communicative) function. The leading direction of language teaching in general education schools, especially in elementary grades, is to achieve students' understanding of the role of language in communication;

Thought is inextricably linked with language, and thought comes to the surface through words. Language is considered a product of thought and does not live by itself outside of consciousness.

Language and thought are secondary to the material existence that surrounds us. Thought is the perception of the external world. The word reflects the conditional name of the concept.

What does not exist in the world does not exist either in the mind or in the language. This situation forms the basis of students' worldview formation and determines one of the didactic principles, that is, language is learned in the situation of active cognitive activity in the process of observing the surrounding environment and reality. Such an approach is the preparation of an answer to one of the main issues of worldview, that is, what is primary: nature (matter) or consciousness; helps students to understand the concept that matter is primary and mind is secondary;

Language is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon, all aspects of which are dialectically connected and united. In the process of communication, all aspects of the language, all its aspects interact with each other, only in such conditions can the language fulfill its role as a communication tool.

It is important to introduce language as a social phenomenon in primary education. The social nature of language is seen in its communication function. To help clearly understand its importance in the life of society, the following aspects should be given importance:

a) during the educational process, it is necessary to ensure that students master the place of each language unit in speech. Pupils learn the communicative function of language in the process of understanding the function of the basic units of language (phoneme, morpheme, word, phrase, sentence).

b) students' understanding that language is a means of communication has a positive effect on finding an answer to the question "What place does language occupy in the life of a person and society in general?". As students move from class to class, the answer to this question deepens and They find examples of the necessity of language in the joint work of people, in the invention of new machines. By developing his thinking and speech, he is constantly improving himself. By changing the universe, a person becomes more mature, and his language also becomes richer is one of the necessary conditions for growth and development.

d) solving (explaining) the "mystery" corresponding to their level about the origin of the language and the emergence of new words in the language has a positive effect on the formation of the primary school students' view of the language as a social phenomenon. The teacher explains to the students that the language was not specially invented by one person, it was created in connection with the work of primitive people and gradually developed.

Language development is not specifically studied in elementary grades. It is important to create a foundation for a scientific view of language as a phenomenon that develops in connection with the development of society. Since the lexical part of the language is mobile and develops quickly compared to others, the development of the language is explained in connection with the development of the society in accordance with the level of elementary school students. Observations of teachers and students regarding the changes in the lexical structure of the language provide suitable material for the formation of students' perception of the world.

In the process of learning the mother tongue, the material that serves as the basis for teaching the mother tongue at school has a special value in solving the issue of forming the foundations of a scientific worldview in students. The ideological direction and artistic expressiveness of the material affects the students' thinking and feelings, expands their knowledge about the environment, cultivates their interest in the language and the people who created it, and increases the level of general development of the students. and affects the formation of their personal qualities and outlook. In recent years, the requirements for the content of the material of the mother tongue school textbooks and the published manuals for teachers have increased

significantly. The main criterion of the material is the knowledge-enriching value of the text and individual sentences, lexical and stylistic accuracy, thematic diversity, connection with different aspects of life, ideological and thematic orientation of the texts, suitability for young students.

Thus, in the process of language learning, the teacher's methodological approach to the formation of the foundations of scientific worldview in elementary school students, the complex of knowledge about language that develops as a social phenomenon that students learn, the way of knowing that students learn, the educational, ideological, political and artistic value of the material that is the basis for language learning has a decisive effect.

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